

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN KINDERGARTEN

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Abstract: At the present stage of preschool education, much attention is paid to inclusion in pre-school education. But many teachers, and mostly parents, have not even heard of the concept of "inclusive education". Therefore, this article briefly describes this concept, history, comparison of the concepts of "integration" and "inclusion", conditions, goals, building the process of inclusive education, participants.

Keywords: pre-school education, human value, inclusive education, child, upbringing, development, family, teacher, psychologist.

Inclusive education is the co-education of children with disabilities and children without such restrictions. It is based on an ideology that excludes any discrimination against a child. In the history of preschool education, several steps can be distinguished from the classical system of special education (assuming complete segregation of "special" and "normal" children), towards education that recognizes differences between people as a value and understands each person as a full participant in the educational process.

The first step is "integrative" education, which involves the creation of correctional classes in mass schools and groups in kindergartens. The experience of implementing integrative programs around the world has led to the understanding that, on the one hand, an individual approach applied to children with disabilities is important for every child, that the methods and methods of teaching and upbringing found in the process of work open up new prospects for children with normal development. On the other hand, it became obvious that the

allocation of "special" classes in schools and groups in kindergarten often leads to the exclusion of "special" children from the social life of schools and kindergartens, creates certain barriers in communication and interaction of children. Therefore, they began to move from the idea of integration to the idea of inclusion – joint education and upbringing of children with different starting opportunities.

The second step is "inclusive" education – it is the recognition of the value of the differences of all children and their ability to learn, which is conducted in the way that is most suitable for this child. This is a flexible system that takes into account the needs of all children, including those with developmental problems, the learning system adapts to the child, and not the child to the system. Benefits are given to all children, and not to any special groups, new approaches to learning are often used, variable educational forms and methods of teaching and upbringing are used, children with special needs can be in a group full-time or partially, studying with support and according to an individual curriculum.

The main purpose of an educational institution in the development of inclusive practice is to provide conditions for the joint upbringing and education of children with different psychophysical developmental characteristics.

The tasks of an inclusive garden:

- creating a cozy, comfortable space for everyone;
- creating an environment conducive to the harmonious development of personality;
- formation of a tolerant community of children, parents, staff and social environment;
- creation of a pre-school educational system centered on the needs of the child and his family. It is not the child who "fits" into the existing education system, but the education system itself flexibly takes into account the priorities and opportunities of different children, organizing them into a single community;

– formation of an interdisciplinary team of specialists who organize the educational process.

In an inclusive preschool institution, the creation of promising, calendar-themed plans for educators and specialists is carried out taking into account both the Educational Program and the individual educational plan. Each event is planned taking into account the individual characteristics of the children who make up the group.

Participants in the educational process:

The organization of an inclusive practice requires new professional competencies from its participants, a revision of functional responsibilities, and the introduction of new specialists. The approximate staff of a preschool institution implementing inclusive practice is presented as follows (the composition may be different depending on the conditions of the kindergarten):

- teachers-defectologists,
- speech therapy teachers,
- educational psychologists,
- social educators,
- tutors.

To coordinate the activities of the teaching staff to include children with disabilities in the educational process, it is advisable to introduce a new staff unit – an inclusion coordinator.

The inclusion coordinator is a specialist with higher pedagogical education – a correctional teacher (a speech therapist teacher, a speech pathologist teacher) or a teacher-psychologist who has experience working with children with various developmental disabilities and has been trained in the field of inclusive education.

Inclusive education has basic principles of learning:

- all people need each other.
- everyone is capable of feeling and thinking.
- the value of a person does not depend on his abilities and achievements.

- everyone has the right to communicate.
- genuine education can only be carried out in the context of real relationships.

With inclusive education, the system adapts itself to the needs of the child in such a way as to meet the needs and needs of all children without exception. The terms "disabled person" and "disability" are fundamentally abandoned here. I would like to note from work experience that the development of a "special" child depends to a great extent on family well-being, the participation of parents in his physical and spiritual development, diversity and educational interactions. Ideally, preschool specialists have the opportunity to help parents resolve issues that have arisen, develop the forms and content of interaction between specialists and parents. It is the family that should serve as a guide for the child's inclusion in a complex and contradictory world. Family and preschool education are two important components of children's socialization. Kindergarten is the first social institution with which parents come into contact.

The most important task of the kindergarten is to "turn" to face the family raising a child with disabilities, provide psychological and social assistance, and involve the family on their side in the plan of unified approaches in raising a child of inclusion. Mutual understanding in an inclusive group is "adult-child" cooperation, but also "child-childhood". This ensures the development of a healthy child and a child with disabilities; support for mutual respect, tolerance; mutual assistance in activities; opportunities to learn from each other; opportunities to help themselves and other children. That is why, in our opinion, the inclusive educational space of the preschool age "Joy of Communication" is a positive atmosphere of acceptance and support.

At the same time, empathy, pedagogical optimism, humanity, love for children, activity of a teacher in interaction with a child with developmental disabilities, etc. are recognized as the basic qualities of a teacher working with children with developmental disabilities.

Thus, a comprehensive impact on the development of a child, taking into account his individual characteristics and psychological and pedagogical support for the activities of the preschool staff, is provided not only by a teacher psychologist, speech therapist, medical support by a medical worker, but also by educators, the administration of the preschool provides psychological support for children together with the Governing Council, the Parent Committee. Parents of healthy children and children with disabilities are also actively involved in the implementation of the goals, who supported the idea of an integrative and inclusive approach and were interested in raising the level of their pedagogical culture.

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